

Role of Social-Emotional Learning on Emotional Intelligence among Adolescents

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ABSTRACT

The present study was aimed to find out the emotional intelligence of adolescents. Survey method was conducted on the stratified random sample of 20 adolescents between the age group of 13-14 years, from an aided school in Malappuram district of Kerala. Self-assessment questionnaire is designed to get about the various five-competency model of emotional intelligence by Daniel Goleman in the book Emotional Intelligence. The data were analyzed using t-test. Results found that there was significant difference in emotional intelligence of adolescents with regard to gender and locality. The findings from the study revealed a significant difference in scores from pretest to posttest. Adolescents may especially need social and emotional help. They're learning how to handle new demands in school and social life while dealing with new, intense emotions (both positive and negative), and they're increasingly feeling that they should do so without adult guidance. They face a variety of challenges, some of which include social, emotional, cognitive, and interpersonal. In order to help them with their emotions, adolescents should be taught a variety of skills to regulate and handle emotions better. Social and emotional learning (SEL) programs are one way to help them navigate these difficulties.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, adolescents and social-emotional learning.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Adolescence is a period of tremendous learning, exploration, and opportunity. Yet it's also a time when behavioral and health problems can emerge or worsen, with negative consequences that last long into adulthood. For instance, people who are victimized or bullied during adolescence can later become more aggressive and more depressed. In the world of technology and advancement, adolescents face a lot of changes, physically, emotionally and mentally, and it is important to understand these, to help them manage their stressors more effectively. Adolescence is seen as a distinct phase of the developmental life cycle in humans and other animal species.[1] With special emphasis to the transition that occurs at this stage, it is seen as a stage rather than an event, therefore emotional well-being plays an important role. With most schools in India, emphasizing the importance of academics only, their holistic growth is hindered. It is estimated that about 15%–22% adolescents have problems relating to social-emotional difficulties prior interventions.[2] Such an awareness demands that the student be equipped with growth of character and a sense of self, to solve their own problems and look at the society as a whole. Research in this area questions the need for social-emotional skills to be taught and they concluded that having emotional intelligence (EI) skills lead to a greater sense of social, academic, and life success, making students more equipped to deal with stressors

The term 'Emotional Intelligence' was coined in 1990 by John D. Mayer and Peter Salovey to describe a person's ability to understand his or her own emotions and the emotions of others and to act appropriately based on this understanding. Then in 1995, this term popularized by psychologist Daniel Goleman with his book "Emotional Intelligence: Why It Can Matter More Than IQ?". Emotional Intelligence is the ability to monitor one's own and others' feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them and use this information to guide one's thinking and action (Salovey and Mayer, 1990). Emotional intelligence is the capacity for recognizing our own feelings and those of others, for motivating ourselves, and for managing emotions well in ourselves and in our relationships (Daniel Goleman, 1995). Emotional intelligence may be defined as the capacity to reason with emotion in four areas - to perceive emotion, to integrate it in thought, to understand it and to manage it (Mayer and Salovey, 1997). Emotional intelligence is an array of noncognitive capabilities, competencies and skills that influence one's ability to succeed in coping with the environmental demands and pressures (Reuven Bar-On, 1997).

Social and emotional learning (SEL) programs for adolescents are appealing in part because they may prevent such problems. SEL programs try to help adolescents cope with their difficulties more successfully by improving skills and mindsets, and they try to create respectful school environments that young people want to be a part of by changing the school's climate. Social-emotional learning is the process through which youth develop the skills

necessary to recognize and manage emotions, build relationships, solve interpersonal problems, and make effective and ethical decisions. There is a growing evidence that the social and emotional competencies youth develop while in afterschool programs can contribute to their success in school and life (Durlak, Weissberg, & Pachan, 2010; Farrington et al., 2012; Pierce, Auger, & Vandell, 2013). As a result, afterschool program staff must understand the most effective strategies to promote the development of social and emotional competencies in youth. They must understand, too, how to build and improve their own social and emotional competencies. This tool focuses on five social and emotional competencies, including self-awareness, self-management/emotion regulation, social awareness, relationship/social skills, and responsible decision making. More importantly, the researchers emphasized that through social-emotional learning (SEL), student's EI is bolstered, giving them an edge in personal and future endeavors.[3]. There are five core competencies that are identified with SEL include:

- a. Self-awareness which essentially deals with assessing one's feelings accurately
- b. Self-management which describes the ability to regulate one's emotions to handle stress and work toward personal growth by the display of appropriate emotions
- c. Social awareness which works toward empathizing and recognizing others' emotions and perspectives
- d. Relationship skills which strive toward effective communication and teamwork
- e. Decision-making which imply the need to rationally make decisions based on consequences and keeping in mind one's well-being.

The present study aims to find out that whether implementing a SEL intervention will affect the EI of adolescents. The significance of this study is to help students understand the transitional changes that occur and how they can better adapt to these changes. There exists a gap in promoting effective SEL interventions in India, especially in schools, where academics is given more importance. The research gap that predominantly exists is that studies done in the past focus more on the role of SEL on academic achievement, than in predicting EI. Studies done in the past have also mostly relied on children, rather than adolescents and this is an important arena to explore. Past intervention target the mindset of children rather than helping them deal with emotions and how to regulate them, and this paves way for more research in this area. Previous studies also look at the long-term benefits of SEL, and this study aims to study the effectiveness of a shorter intervention on the impact of EI. Finally, SEL aims to target effective classroom interactions with teachers, rather than peers, and thus this needs to be worked on.

Objectives of the study

- To assess the emotional intelligence of male and female respondents.
- To provide the social and emotional learning (SEL) as an intervention to improve emotional intelligence. Of respondents.
- To find the impact of intervention of the respondents.
- To check the differences in scores from pretest to posttest.

Background of the study

Early and Middle Adolescence

Adolescence begins at puberty and ends with independence from adults. In this article, I call childhood the elementary years before fifth grade, early adolescence roughly fifth to seventh grade, and middle adolescence roughly eighth to 12th grade. I say "roughly" because these labels are imprecise. Adolescents begin puberty at very different times. Girls mature earlier than boys, and even within genders it's normal for people to begin puberty two to three years apart. Moreover, different racial and ethnic groups in the United States tend to start puberty at different times. For instance, it is normal for African American girls to begin puberty at age 7 or 8; white and Asian American girls often begin several years later[4] Until more SEL program evaluators measure indicators of pubertal status, such as secondary sex characteristics or levels of the hormones testosterone or estradiol, it will be hard to separate biological maturation from chronological age and school year when trying to understand why programs show different effects at different ages.

What Changes during Adolescence?

The onset of puberty means that adolescents pay more attention to social cues that signal possible threats to status or respect, and they exhibit greater reactivity to feedback about status or respect (thrill of pride or admiration, fear of humiliation or shame, or anger at unfairness). They also experience increased motivation to engage in social learning situations relevant to status and respect (those that create acceptance).[5]

Hormones

Pubertal maturation leads to increases or changes in the functioning of a number of hormones, including testosterone, estradiol, cortisol, oxytocin, and dehydroepiandrosterone (DHEA-S).[6]. All of these hormones are related to social and emotional functioning, but so far, testosterone has shown the clearest link to what SEL programs might typically do right or wrong.

In both males and females, pubertal maturation leads to a surge in the production of testosterone. Contrary to popular stereotypes, testosterone isn't an aggression hormone, and it isn't purely a sexual-desire hormone. It's also a status-relevant hormone. When people's testosterone levels are high, they're more likely to focus their attention on markers of status and to respond powerfully when their status is on the line.[7] For example, one study found that testosterone predicts aggressive behavior when boys have deviant friends but leadership when they don't—demonstrating how it focuses attention on the criteria for status.[8]

Psychological Needs

Along with biological changes, adolescents experience psychosocial changes. Bradford Brown, a developmental psychologist at the University of Wisconsin, wrote in a report for the National Academy of Sciences that adolescents have four developmental tasks:[9]

1. To stand out: to develop an identity and pursue autonomy;
2. To fit in: to find comfortable affiliations and gain acceptance from peers;
3. To measure up: to develop competence and find ways to achieve, and
4. To take hold: to make commitments to particular goals, activities and beliefs.

When SEL programs honor adolescents' desire to achieve these tasks—that is, when they respect the kind of person an adolescent needs and wants to be—they can capture adolescents' motivation to change. When programs threaten that desire instead, they may not change behavior.

Skills, Climate, and Mindsets

Different people sometimes mean very different things when they talk about SEL programs. One perspective is that the child needs to be changed—that the child's skills need to be supplemented or revised in some way, and the program will teach the child to do that. This is the skills model. Another perspective is that the environment needs to be changed—that the teachers and other grown-ups in the school need to change the emotional climate to be less negative and more supportive. This is the climate model. Research offers evidence for and against both. One perspective sits between the two: the mindsets model. Environments can socialize children and adolescents to hold different belief systems, or mindsets.[10] These mindsets in turn cause them to use (or not use) the skills that they have or are acquiring.

In general, the skills model of SEL seems less effective with adolescents than it is with younger children. The climate model can be powerful, but it doesn't always translate into positive behavior when children leave the affected climate (for example, when they're out of school and on their own, or after the program ends). The mindsets model is promising for producing internalized, lasting change, because it's a mental model that stays with people over time. The evidence I present below suggests that the ideal is to create a supportive emotional climate that also teaches young people mindsets they can apply when they eventually leave that climate.

2. METHODOLOGY;

Sample

The sample comprised 20 eighth grade students (10 males and 10 females), who were currently pursuing formal education in an aided school. The participants ranged in age from 13 to 14 years. All the participants were residents of Malappuram district of Kerala. Students obtaining grades from A to C were enrolled. These were the only grades seen throughout the sample and hence were included. The participants had both parents present at their home, and single-parent families were excluded. The method obtained to derive the sample was random sampling.

Research design

The research design used was a quantitative design focusing on a within-subjects type. The participants were tested on the EI questionnaire before the intervention, and following the intervention, they were again tested on the same, employing a quasi-experimental design using prepost type of study design.

Tools used

The self-assessment questionnaire is used to collect data from the respondents. This scale was based on the five-competency model of emotional intelligence by Daniel Goleman in the book Emotional Intelligence. The scale can be used for ages 12 and above. The five competences of emotional intelligence which includes:

- **Self-awareness**

The ability to recognize what you are feeling, to understand your habitual emotional responses to events and to recognize how your emotions affect your behaviour and performance.

- **Managing emotions**

The ability to stay focused and think clearly even when experiencing powerful emotions.

- **Motivating oneself**

The ability to use your deepest emotions to move and guide you towards your goals.

- **Empathy**

The ability to sense, understand and respond to what other people are feeling.

- **Social skill**

The ability to manage, influence and inspire emotions in others

The intervention module used was conducted thrice a week for a period of 60–90 min, developed and executed by the researcher. The intervention was broadly divided into three phases: Introduction and Rapport building, Middle phase, and end phase. Each phase had a devised set of activities for the day. The aim of the intervention was to inculcate the values of the SEL framework, thereby developing competencies and learning those skills. Applying these in various settings was the broader objective of the study, and during the intervention, these were applied. Thus, suggestions and the need for improvement were suggested during the session, and the adolescents were asked to practice this both at home and school

3.ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS:

The researcher requested permission from the authorities of the school authority before the social emotional intervention. The data collected from the participants and the outcomes obtained from the results are kept confidential and were utilized only for this research study.

The participants were debriefed after each activity was conducted and told about the risks and benefits involved. They were given the liberty to withdraw at any point if they felt uncomfortable. Most importantly, consent was obtained from the participants, and an assent form from the institution and parents before the commencement of the intervention.

4.RESULTS:

While examining the subscales of the EI Scale, five dimensions were analyzed: Self-awareness, Managing emotions, Motivating oneself, Empathy and Social skill. The mean and standard deviation for these subscales with respect to gender and pretest/posttest scores are provided. It can be observed that there is an increase in the mean scores in all dimensions from pretest to posttest, and this trend is observed in both males and females. To analyze the difference between pretest and posttest scores, a paired sample t-test was computed, as the data were normally distributed. When comparing the overall scores of EI, the t value was found to be – 4.66, which is significant at an alpha level of 0.05. Thus, it can be said that the intervention had a statistically significant effect on the scores of students from pretest to posttest.

5.DISCUSSION:

The main objective was to see if there is any difference in scores between scores on EI from pretest to posttest. The results indicated in that a statistically significant difference with respect to pretest and posttest scores on the EI scale was found, and thus it can be said that the intervention had an effect on the scores of EI. Adolescents experienced an increase in confidence in some of their abilities post the intervention, which targeted facets such as handling emotions, regulating emotions, building social-awareness through empathy, and being self-aware. There seems to be a 2-point increase in scores on an average in both males and females. This finding is consistent with previous studies that suggest that in all the stages of development, during adolescence the level of emotional turmoil experienced is the maximum and through an appropriate intervention, these emotions can be taught to handle well.

The findings of the study revealed no overall statistically significant gender difference in scores of EI, although scores on EI have been statistically different among males and females separately. Consistent with several other studies, in certain domains such as emotional regulation and handling emotions, females are better while males are better in identifying and labelling their emotions and understanding the social context.[11,12] Although significant links between EI and well-being for both men and women have been reported, other studies have found EI to be more strongly related to psychological health and adjustment for female students,[13] who may be more likely to experience well-being when their interpersonal relationships are positive and supportive. Furthermore, peers who have the greatest influence on adolescents and those whose support is most important to adolescents are their close friends.[14]

6. CONCLUSIONS:

The findings of this study have established that an SEL intervention had significant effect on the scores of EI, although no differences with respect to gender were identified. Although this gender difference is not seen in scores collectively between males and females, individually, there exist differences in gender with respect to subscales, where males are better able to handle emotions and understand them, while females are better at empathy and understanding motivation. Previous researchers have argued that females have better EI as they are better able to name and regulate their emotions as compared to males. The findings imply that the intervention, a short-term intervention could have been an immediate and direct solution for the adolescents and thus a change in scores has been obtained. It also implies that how we have been taught to express and regulate emotions during childhood impacts how we deal with situations in adult life. The attachments we experience during childhood have a significant impact on our self-image and how we grow up to associate with others. The level of gender differences in EI suggests that males and females might be influenced by the childhood patterns of socialisation and freedom of expression, among the existing stereotypes put forth by society. Again, interacting with diverse nature of people might help in shaping the extent to which both males and females learn to live with others as a means of preventing social disapproval.

Limitations

This study cannot be generalised to a rural population and hence is limited in its application. Another significant factor that impacted the study was time; the duration was a short-term intervention, but a week of intervention would have resulted in rapid learning but the rates of forgetting would be higher in future. Therefore, spacing the sessions at least 1 week per session could be done in future.

7. FUTURE DIRECTIONS:

First, the findings from this study suggest that although a short-term intervention helps in boosting one's EI, several other factors such as close supportive relationships with parents and peers can be linked to adolescent self-esteem, which in turn affects expression of emotions. Thus, future researchers need to examine the potential mediating factors that might account for some of the associations between SEL and other components such as family environment, type of socialisation, IQ. Second, this study adds to the sparse literature examining the effects of an intervention of SEL on EI, especially in adolescents. These findings are consistent with theory that prosocial behaviour, a component of EI is linked with adolescent well-being in adolescence. Finally, these findings suggest that programs designed to foster EI in adolescence need to consider fostering empathy and prosocial behaviors in addition to promoting positive relationships with peers and parents.

Subscales understanding emotions, motivating oneself, empathy, and handling emotions were analyzed, and a significant difference in scores from pretest to posttest was found only in two dimensions,

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